

Ethylenediamine Complexes of Quinquevalent Molybdenum

H. K. SAHA & A. K. BANERJEE

Pure Chemistry Department, University College of Science, Calcutta-9

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Two new ethylenediamine complexes of quinquevalent molybdenum have been isolated and studied. The nonelectrolytic paramagnetic complex $[\text{MoOBr}_3\text{.en}]$ (where en = $\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$) has been isolated by dehydrohalogenation of the salt $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in solid state in inert atmosphere. These compounds have been characterised by analytical, magnetochemical and spectrochemical methods.

Usually, the organic amines which are fairly or strongly basic in nature do not coordinate with molybdenum in its unusual oxidation state owing to the precipitation of the hydroxide $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_3$. In an attempt to prepare the hitherto unknown nonelectrolytic paramagnetic complex with ethylenediamine as a ligand, we thus first of all prepared the salt $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in bright reddish brown crystalline form in pure state and then dehydrohalogenation was effected in solid state to obtain the black crystalline $[\text{MoOBr}_3\text{.en}]$. Both these compounds have been studied by various physicochemical methods.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Analysis: Molybdenum was estimated gravimetrically by decomposing the compound with sodium peroxide which produced alkali-molybdate(VI) and then on adding Na_2S -solution, thiomolybdate was formed. This on acidification with dilute sulphuric acid, gave molybdenum sulphide (MoS_3) which was ignited at 520° to constant weight as MoO_3 . Bromine was estimated as silver bromide in the filtrate and washings. Nitrogen was estimated using Duma's method.

Preparation: About 4.0 g of molybdenum trioxide were slowly boiled with 30 ml. of 48% hydrobromic acid almost to dryness. The residue was again dissolved in 25 ml. of the same acid and was again evaporated almost to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 30 ml. of hydrobromic acid. Ethylenediaminedihydrobromide (prepared from 2 ml. of the amine and requisite quantity of hydrobromic acid) was added and stirred well. At this stage some solid separated (mostly ethylenediammoniumdihydrobromide), which was filtered out. Pure and dry hydrogen bromide gas was then passed through the clear filtrate which was kept cooled in freezing mixture when a reddish brown solid was obtained. This was filtered, washed, and finally dried over solid KOH in a vacuum desiccator. Yield was about 1 g.

Found: Mo, 16.92%; Br, 69.39%; N, 4.69%; *Calculated* for $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ i.e., $\text{C}_2\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{MoOBr}_5$: Mo, 16.72%; Br, 69.66%; N, 4.88%.

Oxidation state was determined by ceric sulphate method¹ and the metal was found to be in quinquivalent state.

Properties : The compound is extremely hygroscopic, soluble in water and the aqueous solution turns turbid on standing, but no characteristic compound could be isolated from the aqueous solution. On boiling with ethanol the liquid turned brown and white solid separated out which was found to be ethylenediaminedihydrobromide. With other non-aqueous solvents like acetonitrile also, dehydrohalogenation could not be effected and no characteristic compound could be isolated. But heating in solid state effected dehydrohalogenation of the compound. For this, about 1 g. of the compound was taken in a glass boat and was heated in a metal-block furnace at 260° for 5 hr in an atmosphere of dry CO₂ gas when liberation of hydrogen bromide gas ceased, a black coloured mass was obtained, results of analysis of which closely corresponded to the formula [MoOBr₃.en].

Found : Mo, 23.14%; Br, 58.52%; N, 6.81%. *Calculated* for [MoOBr₃.en] i.e., MoOBr₃C₂H₈N₂ : Mo, 23.31%; Br, 58.25%; N, 6.80%.

In this compound also molybdenum was found to be in oxidation state five by ceric sulphate titration.

Fig. 1 Ethylenediammonium octopentabromomolybdate (V) $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in water

Measurement of Magnetic Susceptibility : This was carried out using Gouy balance having a field strength 8500 gauss. The values of effective moments were found out using the formula $\mu_{eff} = 2.839 (M.T.)^{1/2}$, where M is the molar susceptibility after diamagnetic correction. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compound	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	$\chi_D \times 10^6$	Temp.	μ_{eff} in BM
$\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	1100	230.0	295°K	1.78
[MoOBr ₃ .en]	1284	155.1	296°K	1.85

where, χ_M = molar susceptibility without diamagnetic correction and χ_D = correction for diamagnetic entities present.

Measurement of Conductance : Conductance measurement was carried out in a dip-type cell in aqueous medium at different dilutions at a temperature of 28° and the results are plotted in Fig. 1. The results show that $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ is extensively hydrolysed and ionised in aqueous solution. Molar conductance of the compound $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$ could not be measured as no suitable solvent could be found for it.

Fig 2 Ethylenediammonium oxopentabromomolybdate (V)
 $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in 9 M HBr

Infrared Spectra : Infrared spectra were recorded using Perkin Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer. The main bands are tabulated in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Compound	Infrared absorption bands				
Ethylenediammonium	523w	550w	567w	657vw	707s
oxopentabromomolybdate(V)	727s,b	975vs	1038w	1135vw	1211w
$\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$	1307w	1410vs	1500w	1610m	3105vs,b
Oxotribromo(ethylenediamine)	628w	657w	785m,b	795m	1000s
molybdenum(V)	1030m,b	1115m,b	1165m,b	1950s,b.	
$[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$.					

where w = weak, m = medium, s = strong, vs = very strong, b = broad.

Ultraviolet and Visible Spectra of the Compounds : UV and visible spectra were recorded in Hilger 'UVISPEK'. In case of $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ the measurement was carried out in 9 M hydrobromic acid and water whereas in case of $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$ the solvent used was acetone. In the latter case the measurement could not be carried beyond 32,000 cm^{-1} since acetone possess absorption bands in this region. The results and possible assignments are tabulated in Table 3 and in Figs. 2, 3 and 4.

Fig 3 Ethylenediammonium oxopentabromomolybdate (V)
 $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in water

TABLE 3

Compound	λ_{max} in $m\mu$	ν in cm^{-1}	Possible assignments
Ethylenediammonium Oxopentabromomolybdate(V)	690	14493	1.75 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(I)}$
$\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in 9M hydrobromic acid	467	21413	71.2 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$
	412	24272	409 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(II)}$
	374	26738	313 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2(\text{I})$
	247	40486	1250 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(III)}$
$\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ in water	303	33003	1325 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2(\text{I})$
	216	46296	6230 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(III)}$
Oxotribromo ethylenediamine molybdenum(V) $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$ in acetone.	725	13793	65.5 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(I)}$
	486	20576	598.5 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$
	420	23810	6576 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E(II)}$
	383	26110	5210 L \rightarrow Mo
			Charge transfer
	326	30657	314 ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2(\text{I})$

DISCUSSION

Determination of oxidation state by ceric sulphate titration and the value of effective magnetic moment indicates that the compound $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ contains molybdenum in quinquevalent state. The effective moment 1.78 BM is in close agreement with the "spin only" value for quinquevalent molybdenum. This is quite in agreement with expectation since $[\text{MoOBr}_5]^{2-}$ ion with a short Mo-O bond (caused by π -interaction) is surrounded by distorted octahedral array of ligands and is expected to belong to C_{4v} point group similar to $[\text{MoOCl}_5]^{2-}$ ion². This π -interaction with oxygen lifts the degeneracy of the T_{2g} level (present in a pure octahedral arrangement) and the lone electron in the 4d-orbital of molybdenum is placed in a singly degenerated $b_2(dx_y)$ level, leaving no possibility of orbital contribution which would be expected if Mo(V) was placed in a purely octahedral array of ligands having T_{2g}^1 ground state electronic configuration. Thus, the orbital moment is effectively 'quenched' in low-symmetry ligand field.

Conductance measurement in aqueous solution indicates extensive hydrolysis of the salt in water, the molar conductance increasing with dilution. In ethanol, however, ethylenediaminedihydrobromide separated out, probably due to low solubility of the compound in ethanol. When the salt $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ was heated in solid state, dehydrohalogenation took place producing $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$

Magnetic data and ceric sulphate titration indicates that in this compound also, molybdenum is present in quinquevalent state. In the case of this compound also, the value of magnetic moment is close to "spin only" value and this is reasonably expected because in continuation to our discussion given in case of the salt it may be said that the number of symmetry elements is expected to be lesser still, producing still lower-symmetry-ligand-field.

Fig. 4 Oxotribromo (ethylene diamine) molybdenum (V) $\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}$ in acetone

IR spectrum of the compound shows a very strong band at 975 cm^{-1} which is characteristics of Mo(V)-O stretching^{3,4}. The very strong, broad band at 3105 cm^{-1} is due to absorbed moisture. No definite conclusion can be drawn regarding metal-halogen⁵ and metal-nitrogen⁶ stretching. In case of $[\text{MoOBr}_3.\text{en}]$, the Mo-O stretching is observed at 1000 cm^{-1} .

The compound $\text{EnH}_2[\text{MoOBr}_5]$ exhibits five absorption bands in the UV and visible region ($200\text{--}1000\text{ m}\mu$) (Fig. 2). In comparison to the chloro salts⁴ it is observed that ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2$ (II) transition is present here ($34,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) but readily followed by more intense ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (III) transition). The transitions ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$, ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (II), ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2$ (I) and ${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (III) have undergone 'red shift'. This may be due to less electrostatic Mo-Br interaction as compared to Mo-Cl interaction, which will place the bonding molecular orbitals a little higher. It is interesting to note that in aqueous solution the intense charge transfer bands in the UV region is present with greater intensities, whereas, the d-d transitions are absent due to loss of single entity of the group as a result of hydrolysis. The electronic spectra of

[MoOBr₃.en] reveals that in comparison to the salt, EnH₂[MoOBr₅], all the first three transitions has experienced 'red shift' as two bromide ions have been replaced by ethylenediamine. This may be due to stronger bond formation between molybdenum and nitrogen of ethylenediamine thereby reducing the bond strength with bromide and oxide ions which in turn causes lowering of the positions of $e\pi^*$ and b_1^* levels². The compound [MoOBr₃.en] also exhibits an intense charge transfer (L → Mo) band at 26,110 cm⁻¹ (where L = ethylenediamine) and in comparison to the chloro compounds⁷ of similar nature this has undergone a 'blue-shift' which is logically expected because the weaker electrostatic bond between molybdenum and bromine will increase the bond strength between molybdenum and nitrogen of ethylenediamine thereby lowering the bonding molecular orbitals which are essentially occupied by ligand electrons, from which L → Mo charge transfer originates.

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